

INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES AND MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *In a rapidly globalizing world, the need to acquire proficiency in foreign languages has never been more pressing. The traditional methods of language instruction are being reshaped and enhanced by innovative technologies. This abstract explores the theme of innovative technologies in teaching foreign languages. From the transformative influence of artificial intelligence and virtual reality to the gamification of language learning, we delve into the array of tools and platforms that are revolutionizing language education. The use of mobile apps, podcasts, online communities online language exchange platforms have created dynamic and flexible learning opportunities. Furthermore, online language learning marketplaces have democratized language education, offering learners a wide spectrum of courses that cater to diverse linguistic interests. These technologies are redefining language instruction, offering learners more accessible, engaging, and effective paths to becoming proficient in foreign languages.*

Key words: *English language, innovative technologies, modern methods, conceptuality, interactive whiteboard, language learning apps and software, online language resources.*

ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ И СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

Аннотация. *В быстро глобализирующемся мире необходимость владения иностранными языками никогда не была более острой. Традиционные методы обучения языку преобразуются и совершенствуются с помощью инновационных технологий. В данном реферате исследуется тема инновационных технологий в обучении иностранным языкам. От преобразующего влияния искусственного интеллекта и виртуальной реальности до геймификации изучения языка — мы изучаем множество инструментов и платформ, которые совершают революцию в языковом образовании. Использование мобильных приложений, подкастов, онлайн-сообществ, онлайн-платформ языкового обмена создало динамичные и гибкие возможности обучения. Кроме того, онлайн-рынки изучения языков демократизировали языковое образование, предлагая учащимся широкий спектр курсов, отвечающих разнообразным лингвистическим интересам. Эти технологии меняют определение языкового обучения, предлагая учащимся более доступные, увлекательные и эффективные пути к овладению иностранными языками.*

Ключевые слова: *английский язык, инновационные технологии, современные методы, концептуальность, интерактивная доска, приложения и программное обеспечение для изучения языка, языковые онлайн-ресурсы.*

Introduction

In the rapidly evolving landscape of education, the teaching and learning of foreign languages have not been left untouched by the profound impact of technology. The theme of

"Modern Methods and Innovative Technologies of Teaching Foreign Languages" is a testament to the ever-expanding array of tools and techniques that are revolutionizing language education. As the world grows more interconnected, multilingualism is no longer a luxury but a necessity, and educators are harnessing the power of modern technology to meet this demand. This theme is an exploration of the dynamic fusion between contemporary pedagogical methods and cutting-edge technologies, offering educators, learners, and language enthusiasts a glimpse into the exciting world of language acquisition in the digital age.

In this era of artificial intelligence and global communication, language learning has transcended traditional classroom boundaries. Innovative technologies have not only made foreign language acquisition more accessible but have also created an interactive, engaging, and personalized learning experience. From gamified language apps that transform rote memorization into fun challenges to immersive virtual reality environments that transport learners to foreign lands, the methods and technologies for teaching languages have diversified like never before.

In this journey through the realm of modern language education, we will explore how these innovations are reshaping the landscape of foreign language teaching, allowing for more effective, dynamic, and culturally rich language acquisition experiences. Join us in uncovering the wealth of possibilities that modern methods and innovative technologies bring to the teaching and learning of foreign languages.

It is the use of innovative technologies in English language lessons is the main sign of positive results of creative activity, which entails increased motivation of students. At the same time, every teacher who uses information, communication and computer technologies or project activities using the Power Point multimedia presentation in English language classes should know that any educational technology must meet the following methodological requirements:¹

Conceptuality: The use of technology should be based on a well-defined educational concept, including a clear understanding of how it aligns with pedagogical goals and is supported by psychological and socio-pedagogical principles.

Systemic Approach: The integration of technology should follow a systemic approach, where the educational process is logical, interconnected, and holistic. Each component should complement and support the others to create a coherent learning experience.

Efficiency: Technological tools and methods must be chosen and used with the goal of achieving results that meet educational standards. They should enhance the learning process, making it more effective and engaging for students.

Flexibility: Educational technology should offer flexibility in content, allowing for adaptation to different teaching situations, student needs, and varying conditions within the educational environment. It should provide options for personalized learning experiences.

Dynamism: The technology used should be dynamic, allowing for adaptation, evolution, and transformation as educational needs change. This ensures that it remains relevant and effective over time.

¹ M. Kholdorova, N. Fayziyeva, F. Rikhsitilayeva. "USE OF HELPING TOOLS IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE". Tashkent: TDPU named after Nizomi, 2005

Reproducibility: Educational technology should be easily transferable and reproducible, enabling other educators within the institution or beyond to use it effectively. Sharing successful technology-based practices benefits the broader educational community. While these programs can empower students to learn at their own pace and follow their individual logic of cognition, it is essential to remember that technology should complement, not replace, the role of the teacher. The teacher's guidance, mentorship, and expertise remain invaluable in creating a supportive and enriching learning environment.

Ultimately, the goal of educational technology is to enhance the teaching and learning experience, and while it may allow students to learn independently to some extent, the role of a knowledgeable and skilled teacher remains central in providing context, guidance, and support in the learning process. Technology should be seen as a tool to assist educators in achieving their pedagogical goals and creating an enriched learning experience for students.

Indeed, in the context of the informatization of education, the role of the teacher is evolving, and they often take on the role of a director or facilitator in the learning process. The effective use of computer technology is pivotal in modern education, and teachers should view it not as a competitor but as a powerful tool to enhance the learning experience. In English language classes, various computer educational technologies are frequently employed to address different educational challenges. Here are some commonly used computer educational technologies in English classes:²

Interactive Whiteboards: Interactive whiteboards allow teachers to display digital content, such as interactive lessons, videos, and multimedia materials. These boards enable real-time annotation, fostering engagement and interaction in the classroom.

Language Learning Software: There is a multitude of language learning software and applications, like Duolingo, Rosetta Stone, and Babbel, which provide interactive language lessons, vocabulary exercises, and pronunciation practice. These programs offer a structured approach to language acquisition and allow students to progress at their own pace.

Language Learning Apps: Mobile apps for language learning are highly accessible and often include gamified elements to make learning fun. These apps provide students with language exercises, quizzes, and real-time feedback, making learning on the go easy and convenient.

Video Conferencing and Online Collaboration Tools: Tools like Zoom, Microsoft Teams, or Google Meet facilitate virtual English language classes. These platforms enable real-time communication, interactive lessons, and collaboration among students and teachers, regardless of their physical location.

Online Language Resources: Teachers can curate online resources, including websites, YouTube channels, and online forums dedicated to English language learning. These resources offer a wealth of authentic content, language exercises, and cultural insights.

²<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/>

Language Analysis and Correction Tools: Tools like Grammarly or language-specific proofreading software help students improve their writing by providing real-time grammar and spelling correction. These tools assist in honing students' writing skills.

Virtual Reality (VR): VR technology can immerse students in English-speaking environments, helping them develop language skills in context. Virtual field trips or scenarios allow students to practice language skills through realistic experiences.

Artificial Intelligence Chatbots: Language chatbots, such as AI-powered language conversation partners, help students practice conversational skills. These chatbots engage students in dialogues, answer questions, and provide feedback on their language use.

Language Learning Management Systems (LMS): LMS platforms, like Moodle or Canvas, offer a centralized hub for organizing course materials, assignments, and assessments. Teachers can use these systems to create structured online courses and track student progress.

Educational Games and Simulations: Language learning games and simulations make learning enjoyable. Games like crossword puzzles, word searches, and language-specific role-playing games provide an engaging way to reinforce vocabulary and grammar.

Digital Assessment Tools: Computer-based assessment platforms simplify the evaluation of language skills. Teachers can use these tools to create quizzes, tests, and speaking assessments, automating grading and providing immediate feedback to students.

Incorporating these computer educational technologies into English language classes can enhance the learning experience, providing a range of tools to cater to diverse learning styles and objectives. When utilized effectively, these technologies empower teachers to direct the flow of information in the most efficient and engaging manner, ultimately benefitting students' language acquisition.

The practical application of computer educational programs in English language lessons, as you've outlined, is essential for achieving specific learning goals and optimizing the learning process. Let's delve deeper into the practical application of these principles:³

Linear Programmed Learning: In English language lessons, linear programmed learning can be applied by breaking down the curriculum into sequential units or topics. Each unit begins with a presentation of new vocabulary, grammar rules, or language structures, followed by practice exercises. After each section, students complete exercises or quizzes to assess their comprehension. Correct answers allow them to proceed to the next section.

This approach ensures a structured progression through the material, ensuring that students build their language skills step by step.⁴

Branched Programmed Learning: Branched programming is particularly useful for English language learners because it allows for immediate correction and feedback.

When students make mistakes in exercises or quizzes, the program can provide explanations or additional practice to address their weaknesses. This adaptability tailors the learning experience to individual needs, helping students overcome specific language challenges.

³ Bekmuratova U. B. Abstract on "Using innovative technologies in teaching English". Tashkent - 2012

⁴ Otaboeva, M. R. The use of modern innovative technologies in foreign language teaching and its effectiveness / M. R. Otaboeva. — Text: neposredstvennyy, elektronnyy // Molodoy uchenyy. — 2017.

Adaptive Programmed Learning: Adaptive programmed learning in English classes involves letting students choose the complexity of the material they want to study. Students can select different language levels or topics based on their proficiency and interests.

For example, more advanced students can delve into complex grammar structures, while beginners can focus on basic vocabulary and communication.

Combined Programmed Learning: A combined approach to programmed learning can be advantageous in English language lessons. It may involve a mix of linear, branched, and adaptive elements to provide a well-rounded learning experience. This approach ensures that students receive a varied and comprehensive language education.

Block and Modular Training: Block and modular training can be particularly valuable for advanced language learners or those with specific language objectives. In block training, students engage in problem-solving, critical thinking, and creative tasks, applying their language skills to real-world scenarios. Modular training allows students to focus on particular language skills or domains, such as business English, academic English, or conversational skills.

Independent Research and Constructivist Learning: In programmed learning, students are encouraged to take an active role in their education. They independently seek out new knowledge in textbooks, online resources, and other reference materials.

Constructing mental models and problem-solving strategies is essential for language learners, as it enhances critical thinking and language application skills.

The practical application of programmed learning and computer educational programs in English language lessons aligns with the modern pedagogical approach that values learner autonomy, adaptability, and personalized learning. This approach empowers students to become active participants in their language acquisition journey, building a strong foundation in English language skills while addressing their specific needs and goals.

In conclusion, innovative technologies are reshaping the landscape of language education, providing learners with unprecedented flexibility and an array of tools to enhance their proficiency in foreign languages. The future of language education holds the promise of a world where effective, engaging, and accessible language acquisition is within the reach of learners from all walks of life. By embracing these technologies, educators and learners alike can unlock the full potential of language acquisition and build bridges across cultures and languages, fostering a more interconnected and understanding global community.

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